

A Review on use of Sunlight in Human Life

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Abstract: Sun made by God, Some sun light is use in the treatment of human disease. Sun light application in human life likegendis of children, cook food, dry clothes, design passive solar home, electricity and photosynthesis of the plant i.e. human is use in plant in breathing of human such as O₂ and food in vegetable form.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sun is the astronomical at the midpoint of the astral arrangement. It is a virtually perfect range of warm plasma, with inner convectivegesture that produces an attractive field via an electric generatorprocedure. The most significant source of vigor for life expectancy on dirt. Its length is nearby one hundred nine periods that of Dirt & corpus is around 330,000 periods that of Dirt, secretarial for nearby 99.86 percent of the entire mass of the solar System.

Fig 1: Picture of Sun

Solar energy can be equally good and wicked for a human fitness. When in the sunny, the human figure uses the UV part of sunshine to variety its own Vitamin D. Without sunblock, ultraviolet sunny can cause suntan and skin growth. Angle of occurrence of the sunshine makes alteration in periods on Mud as healthy as in the distance of daytime and nightly.

I. SUN LIGHT

Sunlight is the nimble and vigor that originates from the sun. While this vigor reaches the muds superficial, it is called as insolation. It is the radioactivity and warmness from the sun in the procedure of electromagnetic influences. The air affects the quantity of solar energy established. While solar energy travels concluded the air, the air engrosses some of it. Some of it is dispersed to galaxy. Some of it is reproduced by vapors. Around 47% of it spreads the Ground's surface. Florae need rays for the procedure of photosynthesis. Throughout photosynthesis, the florae use the vigor of the sunshine, H₂O (water), and CO₂ (Carbon di oxide), to create C₆H₁₂O₆ (Glucose). The C₆H₁₂O₆ (Glucose) can advanced be charity by the vegetal for wildlife eatsor vigor. The vegetal and the C₆H₁₂O₆ (Glucose) in it. Florae need sunshine to produce green. Wanting enough sunshine but with sufficient water, the vegetal produces very tall actual quickly, but expressions yellow and parched, although when warmed, the leaves are actual moist. Solar radiometer is an expedient that exactly measures the sunlight's strength. The distance of Sun and Earth is One hundred forty nine point six million kilometer, the sun light reached in the earth from Eight minute & Twenty seconds.

- ❖ *Color of Sun Light*-Yellow, Orange, Red, Green, Violet, Blue, White

A. Planets in Solar System

The all planets is around the sun-

Table1: Planets in Solar System

Planet	Distance from the Sun (mK)	Rotation Period	Diameter (Km)	Temp (k)
Earth	149.6	24 hours	12576	260-310
Jupiter	778.3	9.84 Earth hours	142.79	120
Mars	227.9	24.6 Earth hours	6787	150-310
Mercury	57.9	58.7 Earth days	4878	452
Neptune	4497.1	19.1 Earth hours	48600	48

Pluto	5913	6.39 Earth days	2274	37
Saturn	1427	10.2 Earth hours	120660	88
Uranus	2871	17.9 Earth hours	51118	59
Venus	108.2	243 Earth days	12104	726

B. Solar Radiation Received by Planet

Table 2: Solar radiation (Min & Max) received by planet

S. No	Name of Planet	Solar Radiation (W/m ²)	
		Min	Max
1	Earth	1321	1413
2	Jupiter	45.9	55.8
3	Mars	492	715
4	Mercury	6272	14446
5	Neptune	1.47	1.54
6	Pluto	0.57	1.55
7	Saturn	13.4	16.7
8	Uranus	3.39	4.04
9	Venus	2576	2647

III . VITAMIN-D

Vitamin D is a kind of vitamin, which does essential to complete from external foundation. It can be fashioned from saturated fatty acid by treatment with sunshine. When the sunny fall on the casing, the ergosterol under the skin changes to vitamin D. Consequently, if somebody stays absent from sunshine for long, he inclines to develop vitamin D shortage. Any other Sources of Vitamin D-

- ❖ Cereal
- ❖ Egg yolk
- ❖ Orange
- ❖ Milk
- ❖ Shrimp
- ❖ Sardines
- ❖ Shrimp

A. Vitamin D are used in Human Body

- ❖ Weight loss
- ❖ Depression
- ❖ Decreasing risk of multiple sclerosis
- ❖ Decreasing likelihood of developing the flu
- ❖ Decreasing chance of heart disease
- ❖ Bone health

II. USES OF SUN LIGHT

Sun light is use in different human life like energy generation, physical work and treatment of disease like gendis syndrome of children. The some sun light application in human life is given below-

- ❖ Cook food
- ❖ Dry clothes
- ❖ Design passive solar home
- ❖ Dynamic sun light filter for imaging system
- ❖ Dynamic sun light filter for surface
- ❖ Grow foods
- ❖ Generate electricity
- ❖ Heat water
- ❖ Home heating
- ❖ Treat water
- ❖ Kills of bad bacteria
- ❖ Skin syndrome
- ❖ Converting high cholesterol into blood
- ❖ Cleaning of blood vessels and blood
- ❖ Increase oxygen content in blood
- ❖ Builds immune system
- ❖ Increase the growth of children
- ❖ Gendis syndrome of children

III. CONCLUSION

The treatment of human in Sun light is decreasing of Vitamin-D in the human body. The sun is best source in Vitamin-D, other sources of Vitamin-D is egg, orange, milk etc. Vitamin-D is very helpful in the bone. On future research sun light are uses in other treatment of human syndrome.

Abbreviations- UV: Ultra Violet; O₂: Oxygen; H₂O: Water

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